

Corporate Legitimacy: A Passport to Iron Law of Responsibility Evasion in Contemporary Business Space

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Abstract

The environment of business in Nigeria is overly getting more complex and unpredictable than ever before. This trend is occasioned by the rapid changes in social, technological, political, legal and economic forces which thus, mount both favorable and unfavorable pressures on organizations in their quest to maintain operational stability amid competition. In the light of this circumstance, organizations in their bid to remain operationally efficient often engage in some unethical behaviors which tend to question their legitimate standing and possible invocation of iron law of responsibility by the society. Following this observation, this paper theoretically examined the linkage between corporate legitimacy and iron law of responsibility evasion in modern business space. In pursuit of this, strategic adaptation, strategic manipulation and moral reasoning were adopted as manifest properties of the predictor variable. Consequent upon extant literature exploration, it was found that the society serves as a host to all businesses, and as such has the power to select in and out any business depending on its observed corporate behavior. The paper in line with the findings, concludes that corporate legitimacy is a strategic passport through which an organization's activities and behavior is given validity and acceptance by the society to prosper. It was however recommended that that for a business to continually escape the wrath of iron law of responsibility and secure legitimacy, managers should embrace moral reasoning option in their quest to establish legitimacy, especially as it allows the organization to peacefully bargain or negotiate with the society on issues of social concern in order bring about a match between business practices and social expectations.

Keywords: *Corporate Legitimacy, Strategic Adaptation, Strategic Manipulation, Moral Reasoning, Iron Law.*

JEL Classification codes: *K2, M1, M14, M21*

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Introduction

All organizations whether private or public, small or large are by nature teleologic. A teleologic organization is one that is goal-oriented. The goals organizations pursue may include profit maximization, survival, market share growth, good public image, expansion (Jaja, Gabriel & Wobodo, 2019); customer or value creation (Drucker & Maciariello, 2008). To achieve these goals in an effective and efficient manner, the management of the organization must take critical strategic

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decisions and actions to get the organization deeply embedded with the society. Getting the organization deeply embedded with the society is about recognizing the power of the society (i.e., external environment) in determining the fate of the organization. Hence, embeddedness orientation emphasizes that to succeed amid competition, organization should build strategic ties with the society. This is as strategic ties help organizations to reach their strategic goals by providing them with requisite resources, such as thick information sharing, technologies, joint problem-solving agreement, coordinated adaptation, reciprocity, promotion of innovation, strong incentives for quality, and access to market (Azoulay, 2004; Gulati, Nihria & Zaheer, 2000), raw materials, finance etc. Strategic ties with the society are particularly important because organizations are not internally sufficient.

Organizations are not internally sufficient because no organization can generate all of its requisite input resources, hence, they all rely on the society (i.e., other organizations) for resources. The society also depends on organizations' products and services to function well, thus, creating an unbreakable interlace between business and society. The consummation of the union between organization and society is premised on mutual trust and benefits. However, society often time dictates the tone of this relationship through extant laws and regulations it rolls out which businesses as a matter of necessity are subject to. Flagrant disobedience to these established laws, rules and regulations is thus perceived by the society as a deviant behavior which must not be left unentertained. In this regard, the society views such disposition as arrogance and an abuse of corporate power and influence reposed on them. The power and influence of organizations is hinged on the fact that they are trustees, they maximize stockholders' capital, they are highly profitable, they provide the society with goods and services, provide jobs to the people etc. As a punitive measure, the society could invoke the iron law of responsibility on such organizations as a deterrent for their deviancy. The effect of iron law of responsibility on an organization is considered detrimental to its image and general health.

The invocation of iron law of responsibility on organizations by the society is a demonstration of abandonment, rejection and withdrawal of corporate power. At this point, the organization gradually becomes a shadow of itself, especially as critical stakeholders may begin to renege their affinity and commitment with the organization, knowing that its corporate legitimacy is gone. A legitimate organization is one that is ethical and law abiding. According to Lin and Sheu (2012), organizations attain legitimacy by complying with social values and norms of the society. So, organization in a bid to get back on track must take critical steps to redeem and vitalize its corporate legitimacy as a gateway to iron law of responsibility evasion. Amid the observed importance of vitalizing corporate legitimacy to avoid iron law of responsibility in the market space, there is still lack of studies linking corporate legitimacy with iron law evasion within the purview of Nigeria business space. Although, several studies have been cited in the direction of corporate legitimacy and organizational outcomes instead of iron law of responsibility.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this paper is to conceptually determine the linkage between corporate legitimacy and iron law of responsibility evasion in modern business management. In congruence with this, the objectives of the study include the following:

- i) To examine the relationship between strategic adaptation and iron law of responsibility
- ii) To examine the link between strategic manipulation and iron law of responsibility
- iii) To examine the connection between moral reasoning and iron law of responsibility

Theoretical Framework

In a bid to offer explanation on the theoretical underpinning of the study variables, the population ecology theory was adopted. This is because the assumptions of the theory clearly explain the great influence of the society (external environment) in determining the survival and success of a business. For instance, the population theory holds that no organization can produce or generate all the resources it needs to comfortably remain operationally alive, hence, all organizations depend on their environment for supply (Power, 2000). Given this dependency on the society, building a strong social relationships or networks become critical (Ahiazu & Asawo, 2016), as well as being obedience to extant laws. Specifically, obedience to extant rules and regulations is the premise on which selection-retention logic is built upon. The society selects in and retains organizations whose activities and behavior are legitimate and selects out those that are deviant by invoking iron law of responsibility on them, thereby fostering their enhanced entropy.

Concept of Corporate Legitimacy

Denotatively, the word legitimacy implies the state of being valid or legitimate. This therefore connotes that any phenomenon that is considered legitimate is generally validated and accepted by the society. In the context of modern business management, corporate legitimacy is used to personify an organization as an entity whose demeanor and activities are in tandem with societal expectations. These expectations are multidimensional in nature. It could be in the areas of social norms, values, customs etc. Dowling and Pfeffer (1975) were among the leading proponents of this construct. In their definition, they viewed corporate legitimacy as a condition or status which exists when organizations' value system is in alignment with the value system of the larger social system in which they are part of. It also refers to a situation whereby an organization's practices satisfy the social expectations of their environment (Scherer, Palazzo & Seid, 2013). This shows that without an organization securing legitimacy from the society, its going-concern goal will be far from reality. Through legitimization, an organization is able to exist, grow and prosper in a society. In fact, this reinforces Rendtorff (2019) assertion that corporate legitimacy is a recipe for business license to operate in a society, and of the supply of necessary resources in the areas of investment, committed employees, business partners, and sales/consumption, political support etc.

With the forgoing views in mind, we may say that corporate legitimacy is like the oxygen that keeps the organization operationally alive. The moment is taken away, one thing is sure, entropy. This is why organizations strive for societal approval in all they do and respond to institutional pressures through adaptation (Schaefer, 2007; Bansal, 2005). The drive to do this is hinged on the fact that there is a social contract between an organization and the environment or societies hosting them. According to Deegan (2000), social contract refers to all those expectations society holds about how an organization should conduct its productive activities. Consequently, anytime there is a disparity between the organization and the societies' value systems, be it actual or potential, the organization's legitimacy status is put to question, and the implication of such situation is that, it puts the continuous existence of the organization under serious threat, as a result of imminent revocation of the organization's contract to continue its operations by the society.

Building Bloc of Corporate Legitimacy

According to Scherer *et al.* (2013), there are three strategic options an organization can utilize to establish or reestablish its legitimacy with the society, namely: isomorphic adaptation option, strategic manipulation option and moral reasoning option.

Isomorphic Adaptation Option

Institutional isomorphic adaptation serves as a means through which organizations maintain their legitimacy status. It is a positive-reactive mechanism in which an organization yields itself to the

demands of emergent legal framework (rules and regulations) without compromise. At this point, organizations strictly adopt isomorphic processes raised by institutional constituents without objection (Rincón, 2014). Isomorphic adaptation demands thorough modification of organization's operational logic and practices to suit the prevailing standards of the society. By doing this, the organizations are seen by the society as responsible corporate citizens that is law abiding. As a result of this observed loyalty to the rule of law, the society sees it as a responsibility to continuously reinforce and reestablish their legitimacy by protecting them from any form of harm or threat against their survival and sustainability. Hence, validating the view of (Deephouse, 1996) that organizations often modify their practices to adapt to societal expectations in order to maintain cognitive legitimacy. Organization earns cognitive legitimacy when it manifests a set of recognizable characteristics that can be used to classify it as a member of a given class of organization.

Strategic Manipulation Option

Strategic manipulation depicts a situation whereby organizations actively influence social expectations by instigating and inducing the perceptions of relevant stakeholders or policy-makers within their operating environment (Barley, 2010). In this context, Pache and Santos (2010) viewed manipulation as the process through which organizations actively attempt to alter the content of institutional requirements and to influence their promoters. Through the adoption of manipulative strategy, organizations induce change in their operating environment, especially when the existing state of affairs are not favorable to their operational survivability. So, instead of adapting to it as it were, what they do is to penetrate or infiltrate the policy-makers' circle in a manner that will bring about a revolution in the way things are done to their advantage. This view also reflects the observation of Hillman, Keim and Schuler (2004) when they argue that in the context of manipulative strategy, societal expectations are mainly influenced by the organizations' political strategy.

Corroborating with their assertion, Barley (2010) maintain that in a bid to alter these expectations, organizations often use lobbying, advertising campaigns and other mechanisms of strategic public relations and impression management. Most times, they adopt what we may regard as divide and rule system. In this instance, these organizations use different strategic ploys to create divergence of interest and division among policy-makers and other critical stakeholders in order influence certain expectations, such as social responsibility expectations, remittance of taxes and other statutory disclosures. This strategy may be said to be more dominant among the multinational companies operating in Nigeria, especially those within the oil and gas sector.

Moral Reasoning Option

This approach to building corporate legitimacy is one that is anchored on dialogue. It utilizes open deliberation and negotiation with the organization's major stakeholders or societal groups. Here, organizations try to pacify or bargain with the society in a manner that yield a mutually agreeable solution which meets the intent of the regulation. According to Scherer *et al.* (2013), moral reasoning option allows the organization and the society to learn from each other, and eventually adapt their positions constructively. Accordingly, Scherer and Palazzo (2007) contend that through such deliberations, an organization argues for the acceptability of its status quo and behavior by the society. The outcome of this is that it reestablishes new match between organizational practices and societal expectations for corporate legitimacy.

Iron Law of Responsibility

Iron law of responsibility is a load or weight no future oriented organization would want to bear. This is because it is a punitive sanction the society imposes on organizations for their dissident behavior. It explains that if organizations fail to appropriately use social authority vested on them,

the society will withdraw it from them. Clearly, imposition of iron law principle on organization is a demonstration of rejection and manifestation of severed business and society relationship. It is a channel through which the society communicate to the organization that it has wrongly deployed its corporate power, hence, a deviant. A deviant organization is one that its operational processes are not in tune with social values and laws. For instance, when organizations are involved in financial scandals, violate human rights, cooperate with oppressive regime to destroy humanity etc., they are said to be antisocial. In the face of this deviancy, the society is forced to revoke organizations' social power. According to Deegan (2002) this may be expressed through drastic reduction in the demand of the organization's products and services; stakeholders may influence government to impose unnecessary taxes, fines and relevant laws to eliminate those actions which are not in consonance with society's expectations; or suppliers and financiers may opt out of their relationship with the organization.

Key Reasons Society Invokes Iron Law of Responsibility on Organizations

I) **Pollution of the Environment** – The need for organization to objectively carry out its activities without hurting the ecological balance is considered indispensable in fostering a lasting relationship between business and society. Hence, organizations must be very careful while they strive toward their goal attainment as any action, they take will have effect on quality of human life of the people, land, water and air. Protection of the environment is particular vital because organizations take input resources from it and in return dump waste and pollute it, which may in the long run not only ruin the environment but also constitutes health hazard to the humans living there (Wobodo & Zeb-Obipi, 2021). This lends credence to Abdulsattar, Najm and Jasser (2017) study, wherein they posit that without ensuring environmental protection, organizations will have to search for new world or planet to pursue their goals. Thus, polluting the environment is considered a crime against human race.

II) **Tax Evasion** – Payment of taxes at the individual and corporate levels is a compulsory civic responsibility and any person or organization (s) found evading it is highly criminalized. It is considered as an unethical corporate behavior to deliberately decide not to pay taxes or even payless of what is due. This is because when such organization is subjected to social audit, its corporate morality is put to question; hence, a deviant.

Therefore, we infer that tax evasion will gradually leads to the evaporation of corporate social power of the organization through the application of iron law of responsibility by the society.

III) **Production of Fake Product** - One of the key objectives of a business as observed in Drucker and Maciariello (2008) is value creation; which is associated with customer satisfaction. As such, no organization can get its teaming customers effectively satisfied by producing or offering fake or defective products in the market. Anytime organizations deliberately push fake products into the market, the society sees it as genocide because of the health hazard the consumption of such products will pose to the people and the society at large. This is why Nakhleh (2012) posits that quality product or service meet or exceed customer expectation and enhances the quality of relationship between customers and service providers. Thus, the reverse is the case wherein the society validates it as fake, they subject the organization to iron law of responsibility by obviously withdrawing their patronage and other ties with the organization.

IV) **Flagrant Disobedient to Regulations-** Beside provision of social infrastructure and security, another critical responsibility of the government in the management of business and society relationship is law making and policy formulation. These laws and policies are designed primarily to regulate the behavior of organizations and individual members of the nation.

Accordingly, Seyfried *et al.* (2019) show that anytime legislations are rolled out in an organizational field, such laws immediately create expectations and pressures on the organizations to conform; and where noncompliance is perceived or observed, stated sanctions are invoked. Consequently, obedience to extant laws and policies (regulatory pressures) enables organizations to receive both economic and social supports from the society (Wobodo, 2021); while flagrant disobedience to them is the fastest route to facilitated entropy through social sanctions. In handling the issue of business legal framework, we subscribe to the use of what Bondy (2009) regarded as coupling strategy. An approach in which organizations sincerely embrace and implement whatever regulations outlined by the government within the coverage of their operational domain or sector.

Corporate Legitimacy as a Passport to Evade Iron of Responsibility

Any organization that seeks to retain its corporate power in the foreseeable future, must strive toward corporate righteousness in order to obtain legitimacy and evade iron law of responsibility. Corporate righteousness orientation instills in organization the zeal and commitment to pursue its long-term goals without inflicting injury on the society. These injuries could be in the form of environmental pollution, tax evasion, production of fake or unhealthy products, incompliance to regulatory framework, human right abuses etc. This buttresses the view held by Lin and Sheu (2012) that organizations attain legitimacy by complying with social values and norms. When organizations pursue its goals with the interest of the society in mind, their legitimacy is further consolidated and the tendency for iron law of responsibility erodes completely; they completely evade such disastrous societal judgement. Legitimized organizations enjoy increased customer patronage, attract investors due to solid corporate image profile; host community protection arising from mutual relationship etc. (Wobodo, 2021).

The foregoing discussion gives impetus to Meyer and Rowan (1977) wherein they contend that organizations incorporate socially rationalized structures, such as: procedures, products, services, techniques, policies and programs to achieve legitimacy, regardless of the efficacy and effectiveness of those practices. By such alignment, they evade punitive actions like revocation of business operating license; media attack, abandonment by shareholders through withdrawal of their capital investment or share, negative perception on the of part of current and potential customers. This again affirms Samairat (2008) work wherein the scholar argued that the search for corporate legitimacy is the driving force behind organizations' response to social pressures. In the same vein, Qu, Cooper, Wise and Leung (2012) opined that organizations' quest to behave ethically is guided by the assumption of institutional theory which states that organizations constantly strive to maintain and increase their legitimacy by synchronizing pressures arising from the external environment. Also, institutional theorists assert that organizations strive for societal approval and respond to social demands by adaptation (Schaefer, 2007; Bansal, 2005).

Conclusion

As observed earlier, the crux of this paper was to conceptually examine how contemporary managers could utilize corporate legitimacy as a passport to evading iron law of responsibility invocation by the society. In pursuit of this, extant literature was painstakingly reviewed; and the findings indicate that the society serves as a host to all businesses, and as such has the power to select in and out any business depending on its observed corporate behavior. The finding further shows that securing corporate legitimacy is the passport to selecting in (acceptance) a business as a good corporate citizen, while iron law of responsibility is the gateway to selecting out (rejection) a business as a bad corporate citizen. Hence, to achieve sustainable legitimacy, it was found that organizations adopt isomorphic adaption, strategic manipulation and moral reasoning options to

manage the perception of the society toward them and ultimately use them evade the wrath of iron law of responsibility. In view of the findings, the paper concludes that corporate legitimacy is a strategic passport through which an organization's activities and behavior is given validity and acceptance by the society to prosper.

Recommendations

In tandem with the forgoing, the paper recommends that for a business to continually escape the wrath of iron law of responsibility and secure legitimacy, managers should:

- i) Leverage the powers of isomorphic adaption option to bolster organization's tie with the society. This is as doing this is linked with obedience to extant business-friendly legal framework, which is a corporate behavior that the society holds in high esteem and a sure source of legitimacy to evade the wrath of iron law of responsibility.
- ii) Adopt strategic manipulation options where the organization is confronted with unfriendly public policies against business rather than flagrantly neglecting them. The use of this option enables the organization to actively query the existing status quo, influence their promoters and lobby policy-makers to bring about a change to their benefits.
- iii) Use moral reasoning option in their quest to establish legitimacy, especially as it allows the organization to peacefully bargain or negotiate with the society on issues of social concern in order bring about a match between business practices and social expectations.

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